

ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

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Heritage Scientist

Digital Tools, Monitoring Practices, and Data Acquisition

Digital Tools or Technologies

Digital Tools or Technologies used to Monitor

Data collected in Real Time

Challenges in Monitoring Conditions

Heritage Scientist

Data Types, Formats, and Interoperability Standards

Types of Data

Data Format

Standard or Protocols

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Data Accessibility, Sharing Practices, and Collaboration Platforms

Data Structure and Accessibility

Use of Collaborative Digital Platforms

Main Difficulties in Sharing Data

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Heritage Scientist 3D Modelling, Digital Simulations, and Integration of Digital Technologies

Use of 3D Models

Use of Digital Simulation

Main Challenges in Integrating Digital Technologies

Heritage Scientist Digital Twin Applications, Functional Expectations, and Future Adoption

Areas where Digital Twins are considered Most Useful

Information or Support expected from Reactive Digital Twins

Future Evolution of Digital Twin

ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

Heritage Scientist

Cross-analysis insights

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TECHNOLOGIES × DATA TYPES	Spectroscopic data (FTIR, Raman, XRF, etc.)	Imaging data (e.g. X-ray radiography, thermography, etc.)	Spectroscopic imaging data (e.g. XRF imaging, hyperspectral imaging, Raman imaging, etc.)	3D data (scans, digital models, point clouds)	Environmental monitoring data (temperature, humidity, pollutants, etc.)	Chemical or physical test results (e.g., chromatography, pH)	Microscopy and stratigraphic data	Historical documentation of previous scientific analyses	Metadata describing sample provenance or analysis protocols
Multispectral imaging (UV, IR, etc.)	8	8	8	3	6	4	6	7	5
Digital microscopy	10	7	7	4	6	6	9	9	7
Spectroscopy techniques (FTIR, Raman, XRF, etc.)	11	8	9	3	7	6	8	9	6
Computed tomography (CT) or volumetric imaging	2	2	2	0	1	1	1	1	1
Photogrammetry tools	4	4	3	5	4	4	4	7	2
3D scanning tools (e.g., laser scanners, structured light)	5	5	3	7	5	4	5	7	2
Scientific data analysis software (e.g., MATLAB, ImageJ, Origin)	9	7	8	2	6	5	6	7	5
Environmental monitoring sensors (humidity, temperature, pollutants, etc.)	8	7	7	3	9	5	7	8	6
Portable instruments for in situ analysis (e.g., pXRF, fiber-optic FTIR)	9	10	9	3	6	6	7	8	4
I don't use digital tools	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

TECHNOLOGIES × REAL-TIME DATA	Yes, continuously (e.g., from sensors or automated systems)	Yes, but only in specific situations or scheduled intervals	No, data are collected manually or post-processed after sampling	I'm not sure / Not applicable
Multispectral imaging (UV, IR, etc.)	5	3	3	0
Digital microscopy	3	3	5	0
Spectroscopy techniques (FTIR, Raman, XRF, etc.)	3	3	5	0
Computed tomography (CT) or volumetric imaging	1	0	1	0
Photogrammetry tools	2	1	3	0
3D scanning tools (e.g., laser scanners, structured light)	2	1	5	0
Scientific data analysis software (e.g., MATLAB, ImageJ, Origin)	3	3	3	0
Environmental monitoring sensors (humidity, temperature, pollutants, etc.)	5	3	2	0
Portable instruments for in situ analysis (e.g., pXRF, fiber-optic FTIR)	4	2	6	0
I don't use digital tools	0	0	0	1

MONITORING TOOLS × MONITORING CHALLENGES	Limited access to high-precision equipment	Complexity in interpreting data	High cost of tools, systems, or software	Integration issues between different monitoring systems	Lack of long-term maintenance for installed equipment	Difficulty in correlating data with actual conservation needs	I don't face particular difficulties
Environmental sensors (e.g., humidity, temperature, pollutants)	3	3	5	4	1	5	1
Remote sensing platforms (e.g., drone-based monitoring, satellite imagery)	2	4	5	3	0	2	1
Scientific data loggers or continuous monitoring systems	3	3	5	2	2	3	1
Multispectral or hyperspectral imaging systems	1	4	3	3	1	3	1
I do not use digital tools for monitoring	1	1	3	0	0	1	4

DATA TYPES × FORMATS	Tabular data (CSV, Excel, etc.)	Relational databases (e.g., SQL, Access)	Scientific image (TIFF, DICOM, RAW)	Spectral data (e.g., JCAMP-DX, SPC, CSV export)	3D file formats or models (e.g., OBJ, STL, glTF, point clouds)	Proprietary software (e.g., Bruker, Thermo Fisher, Agilent)
Spectroscopic data (FTIR, Raman, XRF, etc.)	10	4	7	6	3	8
Imaging data (e.g. X-ray radiography, thermography, etc.)	10	3	10	6	1	6
Spectroscopic imaging data (e.g., XRF imaging, hyperspectral imaging, Raman imaging, etc.)	9	3	8	6	1	7
3D data (scans, digital models, point clouds)	5	3	5	2	5	2
Environmental monitoring data (temperature, humidity, pollutants, etc.)	8	5	8	3	3	7
Chemical or physical test results (e.g., chromatography, pH)	7	2	7	6	1	5
Microscopy and stratigraphic data	7	3	7	6	3	8
Historical documentation of previous scientific analyses	10	5	11	7	4	7
Metadata describing sample provenance or analysis	8	2	7	5	1	6

COLLABORATIVE PLATFORMS × SHARING DIFFICULTIES	Compatibility issues between different software and data formats	Legal or institutional restrictions on data dissemination	Lack of adequate digital infrastructure for data storage and access	Concerns about intellectual property and data misuse	Limited collaboration between heritage scientists and other professionals	I have no difficulties in sharing data
Yes, platforms internal to my institution	6	6	4	3	4	2
Yes, external or open-source platforms (e.g., GitHub, LabArchives)	2	0	3	2	3	1
No, but I'd be interested in using them	4	3	2	4	2	1
No, I don't see their usefulness	0	0	0	0	1	0

3D MODELS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	High cost of instruments or software licenses	Limited training opportunities	Low interoperability between tools and systems	Lack of institutional support or infrastructure	Resistance to adopting new digital practices	Difficulty adapting traditional workflows to digital methods	No significant challenges
Yes, frequently	3	2	4	4	0	1	1
Yes, occasionally	4	4	5	4	3	3	1
No, but I would be interested	5	3	3	3	5	4	1
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

3D MODELS × DIGITAL TWIN USE CASE	Material degradation modelling and prediction	Environmental impact assessment	Preventive conservation planning	Scientific visualization and comparative studies	Data integration from multiple diagnostic sources	Training and education in heritage science	I don't see relevant applications
Yes, frequently	5	1	4	5	5	4	0
Yes, occasionally	4	7	6	6	6	6	0
No, but I would be interested	5	3	4	6	3	5	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

SIMULATIONS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	High cost of instruments or software licenses	Limited training opportunities	Low interoperability between tools and systems	Lack of institutional support or infrastructure	Resistance to adopting new digital practices	Difficulty adapting traditional workflows to digital methods	No significant challenges
Yes, frequently	3	2	1	2	1	2	0
Yes, occasionally	2	1	3	1	0	1	2
No, but I would be interested	7	5	8	7	7	5	1
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	0	1	0	1	0	0	1

SIMULATIONS × REACTIVE DIGITAL TWIN SUPPORT	High-resolution diagnostic imaging data (e.g., multispectral, radiography)	Environmental sensor data (e.g., temperature, humidity, pollutants)	Predictive simulations of degradation processes	Virtual testing of conservation treatments	Integrated datasets from past campaigns and publications	Alerts and notifications for critical condition changes
Yes, frequently	2	3	2	1	2	3
Yes, occasionally	5	5	3	5	3	4
No, but I would be interested	7	6	8	6	8	4
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	2	0	0	0	2	1